

Why is colour special? Fundamental differences between red and blue quasars

Victoria A. Fawcett

Centre for Extragalactic Astronomy, Department of Physics, Durham University, DH1 3LE, UK

Quasi-stellar objects (QSOs), also known as quasars, are the most powerful class of Active Galactic Nuclei (AGN). Due to the unobscured view of the SMBH accretion disc (AD), which peaks in the ultra-violet (UV), the majority of Type 1 QSOs have very blue optical colours. However, there is a small but significant subset with redder optical-infrared colours (referred to as “red QSOs”).

Although red QSOs have been well studied in the literature (e.g., [1, 2]), there are still conflicting views on how red and blue QSOs are related. Some studies suggest they are intrinsically the same objects, with a red QSO simply representing a blue QSO observed at a higher inclination to the putative dusty torus, while other studies suggest an evolutionary scenario whereby a red QSO is a short-lived phase in QSO evolution. In order to distinguish between these two scenarios, in our work we have explored the radio and spectral properties of a sample of optically-selected red and blue QSOs [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8].

To select our colour-selected samples we use the g^* (4770 Å) and i^* (7625 Å) band extinction-corrected photometry in the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) DR14 catalogue [9]. We define our red and blue “control” QSOs (hereafter, rQSOs and cQSOs) as the top 90th percentile and middle 50th percentile of the observed SDSS $g^* - i^*$ distribution, respectively; therefore, the cQSOs represent typical QSOs in terms of their colour (see Figure 1 and [2, 3, 4] for more details).

In the following we summarise recent results from [3, 5, 8], exploring the radio and spectral properties of optically-selected rQSOs and how these compare to typical cQSOs.

Figure 1: $g^* - i^*$ vs redshift for our sample of optically-selected rQSOs (red) and cQSOs (blue): the rQSOs and cQSOs represent the top 10% and median 50% of the $g^* - i^*$ distribution, respectively, as a function of redshift. See [2] for more details.

Enhanced radio emission in red QSOs

To explore the radio properties of our rQSOs, we matched the colour-selected samples to four different radio surveys: Faint Images of the Radio Sky (FIRST; 1.4 GHz), LOFAR Two-meter Sky Survey DR1 (LoTSS; 120–168 MHz), VLA Stripe 82 (S82; 1.4 GHz), and VLA COSMOS 3GHz (C3GHz; 3 GHz). See [5] and references therein for more details.

Exploring the radio-loudness parameter (\mathcal{R} ; defined here as the $L_{1.4\text{GHz}}$ to $L_{6\mu\text{m}}$ ratio; see [2] for more details), we calculated the enhancement in the radio-detection fraction of the rQSOs in the four different radio surveys (see our previous studies for more details [2, 3, 4]). Figure 2 displays the radio enhancement for the FIRST- (shaded orange), combined S82+C3GHz- (shaded blue), and LoTSS- (shaded magenta)-detected samples plotted as a function of \mathcal{R} . All three of these samples peak around $\mathcal{R} \sim -4.5$ with a factor ~ 3 – 6 excess in the radio enhancement for rQSOs, decreasing to around unity towards the extreme radio-loud and radio-quiet values.

Figure 2: Radio-detection enhancement as a function of radio-loudness (\mathcal{R}) for the different radio-detected samples. The radio enhancement of the C3GHz rQSOs with radio emission dominated by SF is shown as a black star, and those with radio emission dominated by AGN processes are shown as green stars. See [3, 5] for more details.

Utilising the rest-frame (8–1000 μm) far-infrared (FIR) data available in the COSMOS field, we define the origin of the radio emission as dominated by star formation (SF) if the measured radio luminosity was within a factor of 3 of the radio-FIR relationship for star-forming galaxies, and AGN-dominated otherwise [3]. Using these definitions, we then split the lower radio-loudness bins covered by our C3GHz sample into sources with radio emission ei-

Figure 3: X-shooter rQSO and cQSO composites; the rQSO composite is consistent with a dust-reddened cQSO composite [8].

ther dominated by SF or AGN (black and green stars, respectively). From Figure 2, it is clear that, at $\mathcal{R} < -5$, SF-dominated sources have a radio enhancement consistent with unity (albeit low source statistics), expected if there are no differences in the SF properties of rQSOs and cQSOs [6]. Therefore, the radio enhancement in rQSOs is likely driven by AGN mechanisms. Analysing the radio morphologies, we also find that rQSOs have a preference for compact (< 2 kpc) radio counterparts compared to cQSOs [2, 3, 4, 7].

VLT/X-shooter properties of red QSOs

Analysing VLT/X-shooter optical–NIR spectra, we explored the extinction, emission and accretion properties of a sample of 40 rQSOs and cQSOs [8]. By fitting a dust-reddened cQSO composite to the rQSOs, we find that the red colours in $\sim 92\%$ of the rQSOs can be fully explained by dust extinction of an otherwise normal cQSO (see Figure 3). The amount of dust reddening in our rQSO sample is modest, with $E(B-V)$ values ranging from ~ 0.02 – 0.23 mags ($A_V \sim 0.06$ – 0.7 mags). We also find a strong correlation between $\Delta(g^* - i^*)$ and $E(B-V)$ which suggests our method of selecting dust-reddened QSOs is robust (see Figure 6 within [8]).

To explore the accretion properties of rQSOs, we fitted a thin AD model to the X-shooter spectra, fixing A_V to the best-fit values from our dust extinction analysis, in order to compute the mass accretion rate, black-hole spin and Eddington ratio parameters. For $\sim 83\%$ of the rQSOs and $\sim 86\%$ of the cQSOs, the thin AD model provided a good fit to the QSO continuum. Since both the majority of the rQSOs and cQSOs are well fitted with a thin AD model, this suggests that there are no significant differences between the accretion discs of cQSOs and rQSOs, once the effects of dust extinction are taken into account. We also refitted the thin AD models to the spectra, this time leaving A_V as a free parameter, and found consistent levels of dust extinction for the majority of the rQSOs. In addition to this, we find no significant differences in the

accretion properties of rQSOs and cQSOs.

Red QSOs as a transitional phase in galaxy evolution

The enhanced radio emission in red QSOs cannot be explained via a simple orientation model, suggesting more fundamental differences between red and blue QSOs. We also find that the main difference between red and typical QSOs is the presence of dust rather than significant differences in the accretion properties. On the basis of these results, a potential self-consistent scenario that links the enhanced radio emission to the dust in red QSOs is one in which the radio emission originates from shocks produced by either an outflow or a jet interacting with a higher opacity ISM/circumnuclear environment compared to typical QSOs (e.g., Figure 4).

Figure 4: A schematic of potential evolutionary differences between red and blue QSOs; a red QSO has more dust, stronger winds, and weaker jets. Credit: L. Klindt & S. Munro.

References

- [1] Kim, D., & Im, M., 2018, *A&A*, 610, A31
- [2] Klindt, L., et al. 2019, *MNRAS*, 558, 3109
- [3] Fawcett, V. A., et al. 2020, *MNRAS*, 494, 4802
- [4] Rosario, D. J., et al. 2020, *MNRAS*, 494, 3061
- [5] Fawcett, V. A., et al. 2021, *Galaxies*, 9, 107
- [6] Calistro Rivera, G., et al. 2021, *A&A*, 649, A102
- [7] Rosario, D. J., et al. 2021, *MNRAS*, 505, 5283
- [8] Fawcett, V. A., et al. 2022, *MNRAS*, 513, 1254
- [9] Pâris, I., et al. 2018, *A&A*, 618, A51

Short CV

2017–2018: Master in Astronomy, University of Warwick, UK
 2018–2022: PhD in Astronomy, Durham University, UK
 2022–present: PDRA in Astronomy, Newcastle University, UK